

IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE ENGLISH IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

Shomurodova Mushtariybegim Zarif's daughter

Karshi State University Roman-Germanic Faculty, Philology and
Language Teaching (English) student

Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the rapid development of information technology, which is one of the distinctive features of our time, as a result of which the educational process is introduced in a new and unique way, as well as the role of computers and information technologies for the perfect mastery of the modern English language. Because the 21st century is the age of high technology, and our modern youth are taking steps towards the development of the electronic world, not only in the spirit of the national era. For this reason, we have to choose a different approach to the process of teaching the young generation. It is time for teachers who aim to rise in step with the times to be ready to enliven the lesson through any ICT.

Key words: Computer, new interactive methods, integration, modernization, ICT.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ

Шомуродова Муштарийбегим Зариф дочь

Каршинский государственный университет, студент романо-германского
факультета, филологии и преподавания языков (английский язык)

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о бурном развитии информационных технологий, что является одной из отличительных особенностей нашего времени, в результате чего образовательный процесс внедряется по-новому и уникально, а также о роли компьютеров и информации. технологии для идеального владения современным английским языком. Потому что XXI век – век высоких технологий, и наша современная молодежь делает шаги в направлении развития электронного мира не только в духе национальной эпохи. По этой причине нам приходится выбирать иной подход к процессу обучения молодого поколения. Настало время учителям, которые стремятся идти в ногу со временем, быть готовыми оживить урок посредством любых ИКТ.

Ключевые слова: Компьютер, новые интерактивные методы, интеграция, модернизация, ИКТ.

ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKDA INNOVATSION INGLIZ TILINI AHAMIYATI

Shomurodova Mushtariybegim Zarif qizi

Qarshi davlat universiteti Roman German fakulteti filologiya va tillarni o‘qitish
(ingliz tili) yo‘nalishi talabasi

Annotasiya: Ushbu maqolamizda davrimizning o'ziga xos xususiyatlaridan biri bo'lgan axborot texnologiyasining jadal rivojlanishi bilan uning natijasida, ta'lim jarayonining yangicha va noyob usulda kirib kelishi hamda, aynan zamonaviy ingliz tilini mukammal egallash uchun kompyuter va axborot texnologiyalarini roli haqida batafsil ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Zeroki XXI asr - yuqori texnologiya asri bo'lib, zamonaviy yoshlarimiz milliy davr ruhiga monand, balki elektron olamdagi taraqqiyotga qadam tashlamoqdalar. Shu boisdan ham, yosh avlodga ta'lim berish jarayoniga boshqacha yondashishni tanlashimiz kerak. Zamon bilan hamnafas qadam bosib yuksalishni maqsad qilgan o'qituvchilar darsning harqanday AKT orqali jonlantirishga tayyor bo'lishlarini davr talab qiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Kompyuter, yangi interaktiv metodlar, integratsiya, zamonaviylashuv, IKT.

Enter. Language itself is a product of the activity of the cognitive system, linguistic units are formed as a result of human thinking. Therefore, "cooperation of fields such as linguistics, psychology, sociology, and cultural studies is a phenomenon based on cognitive activity. The main task and goal of cognitive linguistics is to understand the environment surrounding people, human history and to check and determine the participation in the study and understanding of the culture and traditions, to study the role of the language that conveys in the transmission of the accumulated knowledge to a certain systematic order, relying on the existing experience in the human mind.

Research and reviews: This activity is called linguocognitive activity. Linguistic philosophy is a trend in analytical philosophy. Denying the worldview importance of philosophy, it asserts that all ills in society occur as a result of language's negative influence on thinking. Accordingly, the goal of linguistic analysis is to clarify language expressions. This stream was introduced to science in 1930 by the Australian logician and philosopher L. Wittgenstein. Pragma linguistics was formed in the 60s and 70s of the last century as an independent branch of linguistics. Also, other branches of linguistics are becoming modern, including biolinguistics; The main task of biolinguistics is to study the biological mechanisms of speech activity, and biolinguistics, in turn, is divided into groups:

- 1. Auditory biolinguistics**
- 2. Biolinguistics of pronunciation**
- 3. Brain biolinguistics**

In linguistics, special attention is paid to mental and mental grammar, according to which all language users must understand each other. Mental linguistics includes syntax and semantics. Lingvopoetics is directly related to art. In addition to ensuring the integrity of our philology, he is an accomplished literary critic and linguist also serves to prepare. Text Linguistics - Beginning in the 60s of the 20th century, a turning point occurred in the science of linguistics. Linguistics noted at this time that it is necessary to study phonemes, morphemes, lexemes and sentences, which are considered language units, by linking them to units larger than sentences. In linguistics, they were called by the terms syntactic integrity, letter head, discourse and text. The conceptual definition of the text is not known. Text classification can be distinguished according to the field of linguistics of the person working on the text. Psycholinguistics is a theoretical branch of linguistics that studies the formation of speech and its theoretical foundations. Neurolinguistics is a modern branch of linguistics formed by the merging of psychology and linguistics. In this, the fact that speech is inextricably linked with the system of the brain when speaking is of particular importance.

Paralinguistics is a branch of science that deals with the means of receiving and transmitting information. Theo-linguistics is a field dealing with the study of the religious language, that is, the study of the meaning of its writings and units, various symbols. Communicative linguistics includes psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, and text linguistics.

What is the use of virtual and augmented reality technologies in education can be justified? For example, let's imagine that the teachers are now Egyptian ehrsams and their always the same stories about building features attract the attention of readers they don't need to give a speech with excessive emotions in order to do so. Virtual reality with glasses (helmets) from the audience along the corridors of sarcophagi they go on a journey, listen to the noise in the labyrinths and it happened thousands of years ago they will be able to independently evaluate important historical events. What are the advantages of virtual and augmented reality? They are human senses allows you to create a receptive environment. In fact, VR/AR is new to you it is convenient for acquiring knowledge and especially for teaching children, teenagers and young adults allows to simulate the conditions. No one thinks for the student, but him will review all received data. Who knows, maybe study VR and AR will solve the problem of "purity" of new knowledge and information in the process. Augmented reality technology, by its very nature, has significant educational potential and this is in the fields of information technology and many others in the

educational system active use of relevant computer tools as a teaching aid in subjects allows. This is typical of many augmented reality technologies and tools indicates its characteristics. In the formation of relevant conclusions, it is relevant in education or partial reliance can be placed on previous research on the use of prior technologies.

In addition, the use of augmented reality technologies in education includes objects and by projecting processes into the real world that learners see helps to increase the level of recognition of objects. Rare insects at school A very popular example of traditional learning is worth noting. Earlier insects cards with photos of insects for students who have not seen certain species was shown. However, when shown examples of real insects, students did not meet. Computer physics has similar problems when learning new material In a fundamentals course, such as studying computer architecture, students have different systems occurs when they need to recognize specific elements on the boards. As mentioned above, augmented reality technologies are in the development stage, Many new approaches and tools are being developed to provide tactile communication substantive, technical and methodological problems still remain without adequate solutions. Informatics The current experience of teaching science shows that the use of any technology should not exclude the use of other technologies. Different technologies a reasonable combination should be sought, including augmented reality technologies must be. Use such technology with non-computer-based learning tools a good example of combining. A simple, printed textbook or a special code that acts as a marker for reality added to the text of the manual, and even images can be embedded, which expands the functionality of such teaching tools.

All language lovers know that English has 4 aspects (reading, writing, speaking,listening) formed.

Reading - used a projector during the lesson to develop this skill

without (in large view) articles, works of art, short stories can be shown to the reader. Some students have strong visual recall skills and learn language through sight-reading they learn.

Listening - in this skill, audios are played to the student using a computer. Hearing audio recording is analyzed in the brain through analyzers. In this case, the student listens as well a native speaker how to correctly pronounce words in his mother tongue learns. Also, in the article "Artificial intelligence and language learning", B. Skinner easily learns language showed the importance of the role of the computer in learning. Not only listening, but also writing on the computer it can also be used in the skill, i.e. in individual training.

Writing is a skill, more complex than the rest because of vocabulary, correct use of grammar is important. Especially social networks its place is incomparable. Students write in English with their foreign peers using the Internet they

communicate. An opportunity to improve writing skills during the lesson through the interactive whiteboard there is. Whiteboards, i.e. interactive whiteboards, were introduced to science by Marty. Grammatical at first used to express exercises, logical expressions. Today, his tasks are increased.

Speaking is a skill in which the student's ability is revealed. What are the language skills?it is shown that it is at the level. With the help of computer technology during the lesson (game through) this skill can be improved. The student selects any of the given numbers on the computer

chooses and thinks about the topic behind it (appropriate for age and level of knowledge) explains. Such methods are in the student's hands as a result of discussion with mutual partners gradually develops the ability to speak.

Summary:In conclusion, it should be said that today the computer is used in teaching foreign languages technologies are gaining importance. Informatics, digital technology sciences as well connected with the methodology of teaching a foreign language. I think it's information technology now learning foreign languages is easy and fast. For this, of course, to young personnel it is necessary to teach them how to teach using modern technologies, to improve their skills in this regard. After all, perfect learning of foreign languages is the way to reach the pinnacle of knowledge is considered.

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